

ART STUDIES

О ЖАНРОВЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЯХ НАРОДНЫХ СКОРБНЫХ ПЕСЕН

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ABOUT THE GENRE FEATURES OF FOLK LAMENTATION SONGS

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Аннотация

Статья посвящена жанровым и стилистическим особенностям одного из уникальных народно-песенных жанров – песен скорби. Сделана попытка выявить особенности воздействия музыки на человека в состоянии горя и скорби.

Основной аналитический материал рассмотрен с помощью сравнительного метода, что позволило установить сходство и различие музыкально-обрядовых явлений в ритуальной сфере, а так же изучить общественно-историческое развитие погребальной обрядности в фольклоре разных народов.

Abstract

The article is devoted to the genre and stylistic features of one of the unique folk song genres - songs of sorrow. An attempt has been made to identify the characteristics of the impact of music on a person in a state of grief and mourning.

The main analytical material was examined using the comparative method, which made it possible to establish the similarities and differences of musical and ritual phenomena in the ritual sphere, as well as to study the socio-historical development of funeral rituals in the folklore of different peoples.

Ключевые слова: фольклор, песня скорби, стиль, особенность, обрядность.

Keywords: folklore, song of sorrow, style, peculiarity, ritual.

Ritual music is not only an aesthetic decoration sad ceremony, but is also called upon to perform such functions as providing proper honors to the deceased; consolation and psychological assistance family and friends when experiencing loss; management of ritual actions during the ceremony. Works whose music are recognized as ritual performs the functions of managing ritual actions, providing honors, decoration of the ceremony and psychological assistance to those present. [5]

The musical memory of a culture about itself does not disappear, does not go into oblivion. Embodied in various self-renewing forms, it constitutes the foundation, the meaning of musical art. In a compressed encrypted form, it stores cultural information encoded in one way or another. As musical codes, symbols, signs, motifs, intonation formulas, timbre grain forms from which musical compositions grow, and the semantic context embodied in them, can be considered characteristic of certain eras, for some genres that define these musical eras.

Dictionaries define the word lament as “feeling or expressing sorrow or grief.” It’s not a word we use much these days. In fact, lamenting is an art that we don’t often practice in Western culture. Rather than express our emotions, we tend to hide them, distract ourselves from feeling them, or even pretend they don’t exist. When difficult circumstances cut into our lives, we are likely to seek out false saviors to rescue us. We bury ourselves in work, entertainment, or a pint of ice cream.

We might even take things into our own hands and attempt to control our circumstances. We’ll do anything but face the pain and heartache we feel. [1]

The terms *lamentation* and *lament* derives from the Latin word *lamentum* [1] and can be equated with expressions such as to mourn, to grieve, to wail, to moan, to weep and to cry. The term *lamentation* is closely linked with the Italian term *lamento* that stands for a piece of music in which somebody expresses his grief over something, mainly over another person’s death. The term *lamentation* when referring to music means in the majority of cases “a vocal piece based on a mournful text, often built over a descending tetrachord ostinato and common in cantatas and operas of the Baroque period. Since the late 17th century also instrumental pieces with wailing nature were sometimes named *lamento*, especially works by J. J. Froberger and J. S. Bach. Lamentation in art is represented just as good as in music: Since the medieval and renaissance times one of the most often depicted topics is the “Lamentation over the Dead Christ”. Painters, sculptors and other artist grew never tired of illustrating Christ and his mourners, because of the importance of the incident of his death for the Christian community.[2]

Lamentation itself is the act of giving expression to one’s feelings of grief; this can be done in multiple ways, for example by means of gestures and stance as well as through sounds and melodies. In consequence, the expression of lamentation can be perceived by others, though the origin of the act is actually an individual

private emotion. However, in music and art, this feeling has to be made public in order to serve the purpose of art which is, simplified, the transfer of expression from the artist to the spectator. As a consequence, the paradox element in the depiction of laments in art and music is that the personal lament becomes a spectacle. This has an effect on how artists decide to present the subject: in terms of a setting of a musical lamentation, the real feeling with its negative and not pleasant implications stays in the background and is transformed into something much more beautiful which still has a sad subtext - this is the contradiction of theatre. In terms of art, there is no such paradox to be seen: in the depiction of mourning and wailing people prevails an approach orientated to reality. As an attempt to explain why that is so, there could be stated that painters try to depict what they see in real life; visual impressions are the source of paintings, being again made into something visual. In respect of music, there is one more obstacle to be transgressed: what real life provides has to be converted into medium apart from real life; into music. [11]

Analysis of the music of folk laments shows that, despite a significant amount of improvisation, performance techniques are quite rigidly fixed in the composition and often play structuring role in the chants, which allows the lamentations to be counted cultural form of expressing sad emotions, as opposed to natural sobs. Thus, we can talk about regulation of the degree emotional stress through the performance of laments and, therefore, about a vivid manifestation of aesthetic and psychological functions in folk ritual music. Utilitarian functions are realized in voices mainly thanks to texts.

Each type of funeral ritual has its own individual musical features, both theoretical and practical sense. If for the music of military rituals the most important are utilitarian functions, then in folk and church traditions to a large extent the emphasis is on spiritual aspects, which leaves its mark on musical language of the works. [3]

In order for the ceremony to gain proper integrity and functionality from a musical point of view, ritual and accompanying his musical material must be coordinated. Thus, there is a need for a musical script that represents is specially designed for each ceremony or each typeceremonies, a document detailing the content of the musical events of the ritual ceremony with instructions regarding them registration and implementation. Lament has a broad thematic scope, it reflects life such realities and events that have an epic nature. Lament is sober criticism, sincere concern. Its lasting orce to be used traditionally by later chroniclers and become one of the important genres of medieval bibliography. The genre and theme of mourning and tragedy are richly nourished, old and new with facts, continues to be relevant.

Since ancient times, human thought has tried to penetrate the secrets of music. One of these secrets, or rather the key one, was the essence of music. There was no doubt that music can have a strong impact on a person due to the fact that it contains something. However, what exactly is this meaning, what does it "tell" a person, what is heard in the sounds - this differently varied

question, which has interested many generations of musicians, thinkers, scientists, has not lost its urgency today. It is not surprising that the fundamental question of music's content received very different, sometimes mutually exclusive, answers. Here are just a few of them, conditionally grouped by us. [10]

When analyzing emotions in a piece of music, numerous difficulties arise, including due to insufficient distribution theories of musical emotions.

In musicology, little attention was paid to the dictionary of musical emotions, and its lexical richness, expressiveness, and accuracy usually depended from the talent of a music analyst. In addition, another fundamental moment: the content of music cannot be retold in words, it resides in its own world of artistic expression. Therefore, it is quite natural for someone who talks about music to be too definite, and in this sense, a "rude" word distorts the subtle moment of musical sound.

It should immediately be taken into account that musical ideas about emotions differ significantly from psychological ones, since musicology and psychology are different sciences, the same terms have specific meanings and contexts in both areas. But in terms of emotional vocabulary. The accumulation of terms in the works of psychologists is so great that they can also be useful in the practice of musicians. [9]

Musical emotions, although they focus on life emotions as sample, have their own special aspect of content, which is always positive.

Lamentations are a genre of ritual folklore characteristic of many world cultures. Lamentations were created as improvisations. The fact that the lament was improvised does not, however, provide grounds for asserting that it is not connected with the tradition of folk poetry. This only means that they were never performed exactly the same way twice. But although they were not repeated in their entirety, when creating each new text, the cryer (or plakusha, crying, as the mourners were called) relied on traditional images that passed from work to work, stable verbal formulas, individual episodes and plot points, independently existing beliefs. Using the riches of folk poetry, the voplenitsy created pictures of real life, talked about really living people, enriched traditional poetic imagery, traditional poetic language with additions drawn from reality, their observations and generalizations. Often, an artistic image that arose from a combination of folk tradition with the poetic imagination of a mourner was remembered, picked up and enriched in lamentations composed by other people in connection with other life events. This is how the collectivity of folk art was expressed in lamentation. [8]

In most cases, they contain sincere, deeply emotional exclamations of grief and express personal grief; their text does not contain deep social generalizations that are found in the best examples of northern lamentations.

Improvisation of lamentations required poetic talent and skills in the use of artistic images and poetic language. To one degree or another, all women acquired the ability to improvise a score - this is a unique

form of specific creativity. Listening to funeral lamentations from childhood, women memorized their details, images, turns of phrase and subsequently used them when they had to mourn the deceased or say goodbye to their girlhood and family of origin. Naturally, from the ordinary performers of lamentations, the more poetically gifted ones had to stand out.

We were interested in the article by Yugas, which describes modern lamentations: "The article researches laments' emic (existing within the culture) attitude of laments towards the question of improvisation. By the material from interviews and comments appearing in the process of recordings of lamentations, it is proved that the idea of lamenting as an expression of grief is part of the laments' emic concept of funeral lament. The texts of the *bailichkas* and oral narratives define two types of laments: a professional one, working for a fee, and a grieving relative, spontaneously beginning to lament at the funerals of relatives, and it is the second one, who becomes a protagonist. Tales of learning the lament also work on this idea. Despite the practice of training before the first lament, laments were to maintain an illusion of spontaneity and personal emotional involvement. Thus, the ethical notion of a lament as a ritual specialist, which was formed as the result of a long and careful analysis of texts and practices, contradicts not only the 'romantic' view of the world of the first collectors of folklore, but also the emotional representation that exists within the culture." [11, p. 37]

The ritual practice of performing lamentations at funerals and funerals in villages include the formula rich text and manner of performance that imitates real physical logical crying. Lamentations communicate with deceased, transfer the deceased to the status of an ancestor (funeral lamentations) or provide patronage from deceased relatives (funeral lamentations). In the 20th century in many villages the tradition remained relevant, but the urbanization of the population, including the penetration of a new funeral scenario and a different mourning etiquette, made it marginal in the eyes of some residents.

As E. Yugai rightly notes, Lamentation researchers paid attention to the melody and the text of lamentations, in a ritual context that allowed realize mythological functions, while looking the performers themselves have never been subjected to analytical consideration. At the dawn of the work of researchers with lamentations the performers' comments were perceived as obvious and corresponding to the truth, were later discarded as false and insignificant. [11, p. 38]

Many folklore texts consist of frozen combinations words that have a specific meaning. In them, as in closed capsules, cultural meanings are transmitted through centuries, even if they unclear to a particular narrator. Those who lament are often not aware of the formulaic nature of the genre.

Most often, modern lamentations are recorded in situational situations of the interview. In this case, the lamentant has the opportunity comment on the text. There are several types of such comments. The first is text assignment. Emphasizes correctness of the stable formula, its applicability to life laments. The following standard elements of demonology are present here:

gical story, like the appearance of a goblin in the form of a man, possibly the possibility of punishment from the devil for improper behavior in the forest, protection from the devil with the help of a timely created cross.

In many cases, when asked about lamentations, the folklorist It is not the text of the lament itself that is obtained, but the oral story about it. And here it is important understand that such narratives also develop according to certain new rules.

Thus, this idea of the lament as ritual specialist, which was the result of a long and careful

analysis of texts and practices, contradicts not only the "noveltic" view of the world of the first folklore collectors, but also emic idea that exists within a culture.

The relevance of the idea of deprivation in the concept in a fundamental sense is that it underlies the opposition, the central noy for chanting as for verbal composition lying transitional rites. This is against re-enactment of the idyllic past, which is characterized by social, mathematical real, ontological, cosmogonic skoy stability, completeness and orderliness devotion, tragic future, sacredness dealing with loss and bereavement. Loss leads primarily to change change in social status: the wife becomes a widow, the husband becomes a widower, children - orphans, a peasant - a soldier, and a girlka - a woman and a wife, - and the rhyme is concentrated on this transition. The semantic-pragmatic dominant of deprivation is found dit embodiment at the actual textual level: its se-the mantic component is formed due to the description and transfers of social, property and psychological sky losses of liminal subjects.

Pragmatic component of the dominant deprivation (this applies primarily to funeral and recruiting skoy) - the reason why crying tells in detail about the suffering and pain experienced and expected in the future ryakh - apparently has a dual nature. [7]

Significant conceptually and explicated in a number of basic themes and motives, the dominant of deprivation requires special linguistic means of expression. Most productive of these are word-forming caritives - words and constructions tions with a prefix and a preposition without, "expressing the meaning of non-shortage, shortage, lack of something".

Striking differences in the number of word formations vocative caritives used in texts of different functional types of crying, explained by the characteristic corresponding rituals, on the one hand, and the features of poetry tics of the texts themselves - on the other. There is no doubt that it is not a coincidence occurrence in texts of lamentations of words and constructions, cohoding an "inconspicuous" and, at first glance, little information tive for the analysis of genre specifics of lexical-grammatical ical element - a preposition and a prefix without. It is the combinations with without are the main way of verbalizing the basic for lamentations of the category of deprivation, which has a pragmatic logical conditionality, conceptual significance and formative structuring the motivic structure of cries.

Conclusion

To summarize the above, it should be noted that if the verbal code quite specifically embodies the symbolic the meaning of each stage of the funeral rite, the sound is reflects its deep emotional and semantic implications. Lament music is an archaic form of acoustic the behavior of the living in their relationship to the world of death.

In traditional culture, the genre of lamentations is one of the most important components of the verbal and musical codes of the funeral and memorial complex.

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